

'Design is a "bullshit" job': The constraints of capitalism as a barrier to fulfilling psychological needs

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As technology and the times change, so has the nature of work. Along with the rise of capitalism has come the invention and increase of bullshit jobs. This paper proposes that commercial design work is a bullshit job as it serves no real practical purpose; rather, it is a political tool to promote consumerism. Furthermore, such jobs do not appear to provide for designers' psychological needs that would contribute to career and life satisfaction. Therefore, designers often face the dilemma of having to choose between work that provides a livelihood and more meaningful work that aligns with their personal values and enhances their lives. It is suggested that designers can use their skills to work within the system to promote change so that they can make a living doing meaningful work that contributes positively to society and their own psychological needs.

Keywords: capitalism; commercial design; consumerism; psychological needs; technology

Automation has now replaced many manual labour jobs and has the potential to reduce the number of working hours and even the number of positions available (Acemoglu & Restrepo, 2019). Nonetheless, some labour jobs remain. With the reduction in the need for labourers, new positions have been created by the ruling class as a way of tying a person's job position to their worth as a person and to maintain the upper class's power and sense of importance (Graeber, 2018). Most of the newly invented jobs serve the purpose of capitalism without generating literal benefits to society and therefore are considered *bullshit jobs*. According to anthropologist David Graeber (2018), '*bullshit job* is a form of paid employment that is so completely pointless, unnecessary, or pernicious that even the employee cannot justify its existence even though, as part of the conditions of employment, the employee feels obliged to pretend that this is not the case' (p. 28). The emergence of consumerism driven by a capitalist society has shifted the value of a designer's work; the intention of design is now to influence people to consume more. In capitalistic societies, design is a political tool that influences people to act in ways that increase the capitalists' profits but do not benefit society in general nor the life and career satisfaction of designers via fulfilling their psychological needs.

Design as a bullshit job

Designers are obligated under the rule of society to do commercial work, even if such work conflicts with their values and intentions and detracts from them fulfilling some of their psychological needs. The ruling class discovered that happy citizens with free time can undermine their authority (Graeber, 2018). Consequently, they invented *bullshit jobs* to distract people by keeping them occupied and directing their hatred towards the unemployed and those with truly productive jobs and vice versa which diverts attention away from those in authority (Graeber, 2018). The design field itself has been historically steeped in inequities and has been used to perpetuate colonisation and oppression of less privileged members of society by those in power (Sloane, 2019).

Setting aside the societal mindset that individuals need to work to be considered valuable, the upper classes and of course the business sector is benefiting from society's emerging trend of consumerism. Since the 1950s, consumerism has encouraged people to value consuming over all else and has subsequently 'shifted the balance in design from a concern with solutions to utilitarian needs to an emphasis on an object's motion, psychological, and social role' (Whiteley, 1985, p. 36). Alongside consumerism, the multibillion-dollar advertising industry has emerged. Providing 5.8 million jobs in the European Union alone, there is no doubt that this industry's main value is to boost the economy and increase gross domestic product (Deloitte, 2017).

Since employers' agendas naturally prioritise increasing their profits, designers as employees have no choice but to pursue the available options at the expense of their own psychological needs. Designers need to sustain themselves by selling their labour in exchange for wages. Since work 'is the active expression of the labourer's own life, and this life activity he (*sic*) sells to another person to secure the necessary means of life' (Marx, 1847, para. 8), this results in designers entering the commercial industry in exchange for monetary rewards that can be traded for utilitarian goods.

Commercial design, therefore, is a *bullshit job*; it does not create a true benefit nor have any meaning for society nor designers but rather just influences the masses to become better consumers. In terms of being a designer, working in the commercial sector is in favour of the few people in power rather than society as a whole. Working in such areas as branding, advertising, and marketing does not seem to add value to society nor enhance designers' well-being, but rather assists in increasing profit for the capitalists and supports consumerism (Relejo-Howell, 2018). Cultural critics view the consumerisation of society as a 'rapidly multiplying cancer of depersonalized mass media entertainment and inauthentic processed culture' (Whiteley, 1985, p. 37). Hence, from this point of view, design by way of consumerism may damage the environment and people rather than uplift society (Walker, 2017).

Considering the aim of advertisement is to persuade consumers, it is designed to induce people into purchasing when advertisers tap into human's innate physical and psychological needs, predict and manipulate their emotions, and design ads 'in such a manner that seem to promise or imply a possible connection between a product and happiness, social acceptance, a good family, a good sex life, intimate friendship and so on' (Danciu, 2014, p. 24). Such use of psychological concepts to manipulate consumers may be psychologically harmful to a moral designer.

During a semi-structured interview conducted for this paper, a current designer stated 'I think doing logos for a brand or branding isn't meaningful because it's useful for the owner but not for society. I don't think

their business is very meaningful such as a finance business since it's just making up numbers to reduce taxes or a packaging company for dried mangoes – it does not contribute anything to society – people just eat the mango' (personal communication, S. Chunharungroj, October 22, 2020). In sum, commercial design is a *bullshit job* that likely detracts from society's positive advancement and may even contribute to the dissatisfaction of the designers themselves and even people in general.

Values and meaningful design work

Commercial design being a *bullshit job* creates a dilemma for the designers who have to choose to stay in occupations that conflict with their values and psychological needs just to sustain their lives; it is difficult to avoid commercial work even if they disagree with their employer's consumeristic end goals or unethical practices because the job still pays the bills. Therefore, they are likely to take Garland's (1964) approach of not advocating 'the abolition of high-pressure consumer advertising' because it 'is not feasible' (p. 1).

Designers must be conscious of their moral stances and decisions to maintain their self-worth. The designers who believe in working for a greater significant cause (i.e., improving social issues) are likely unable to financially sustain themselves solely by participating in advocacy work or by working for charitable organisations since work should be something that fulfils both a person's physical and psychological needs; work should be paid but also coincide with the person's values and interests (Holland, 1997; Savickas, 2005). Moreover, people's psychological needs involve contributing to something greater than oneself which can lead to greater meaning in life (Seligman, 2011; Van Tongeren et al., 2015). In contrast, if work is meaningless, it can lead to a person experiencing boredom and resentment (Bargdill, 2000).

In comparison to engaging in meaningless work, some people describe their careers as a 'calling': a meaningful career that 'fits' the person, is intrinsically motivating, prosocially contributes beyond oneself, and the individual has a sense that they are living their intended purpose (Dik & Duffy, 2009). Such work potentially meets some psychological needs and could contribute to a designers' life and career satisfaction. For example, when people have chosen to change their careers to one that they consider their calling, they tend to feel that they are serving the greater good and that their new career is more meaningful, fulfilling, and infused into their identities (Ahn et al., 2017). Not only that but if someone believes that their work is a calling, they tend to believe their life has greater meaning and feel more satisfied with their careers and life (Duffy & Dik, 2013). The positive outcomes increase even more if people are actually 'living' their calling as opposed to just 'having' a calling but not pursuing it (Duffy & Autin, 2013; Duffy et al., 2013). And the opposite seems to be true: if someone believes they have a calling but experience barriers to being able to participate in it, the outcomes tend to be negative (Berg et al., 2010). Therefore, it would seem reasonable to conclude that when designers conduct work that does not align well with their values and that they perceive as not contributing positively to society in general and their psychological needs in particular, they will be more likely to have diminished work and life satisfaction and possibly even become depressed due to learned helplessness (Seligman, 1972).

Living one's calling also involves a moral component that one is doing the right thing, and people may be willing to make sacrifices to some of their physical needs to do so (Bunderson & Thompson, 2009). Furthermore, having a calling may be associated with someone's readiness to do work related to their calling (Lau et al., 2020). Likely of relevance to designers who probably value such influences on their work, career calling is associated with both work passion and innovation performance (Liu et al., 2021). In sum, if designers were able to pursue their callings while still being able to earn a living (as opposed to engaging in *bullshit work*), they probably would have a greater chance of fulfilling their psychological needs and report increased life and career satisfaction.

While it currently seems almost impossible to rely only on work that is consistent with designers' values and contributes to their psychological need fulfilment, it is possible to work toward such an ideal. For instance, Jonathan Barnbrook (n.d.), an active designer, states he chooses to work on projects that are in alignment with his beliefs: 'We don't work with companies we don't agree with, which has cost us a lot of money,' (The Political Role of Design, para. 4). Chunharungroj (2020), on the other hand, chooses to work on both commercial jobs that do not necessarily align with her values and jobs for non-profit organisations. Even though she does not get paid for humanitarian work, she finds such work to be meaningful and fulfilling. Hence, if the designer is conscious of their moral values, it would be advantageous for them to make decisions that are less contradicting or that sustain their values and helps meet their psychological needs.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, design can be considered a *bullshit job* as part of a political profession due to the obligation of the designers to design for those in power. Under the current economic system, people need to work in exchange for a living and that has led to designers choosing work that relies on extrinsic monetary rewards even though it contradicts their values and does not allow them to meet their psychological needs. They may be intrinsically motivated to pursue meaningful work that fits with their sense of career calling; however, with political constraints, designers are required to work in a specific design industry due to the demand of the market resulting in inadequate opportunities to work for significant causes that they believe in, possibly leading to reduced life and career satisfaction and even depression.

Further research is needed to better understand the adverse effect of the nature of commercial design work being a *bullshit job* and how that affects designers' career and life satisfaction and their ability to get psychological needs met through work. While only one current designer was interviewed and another published interview was reviewed for this current paper, their lived experience of the challenges of finding meaningful paid work and feeling more satisfied when engaging in more meaningful work, even if *pro bono* (Barnbrook, n.d.; personal communication, S. Chunharungroj, October 22, 2020), can help guide future studies.

For designers to work to their full potential, the power of the current system must be re-balanced. It would be compelling to see if the designers themselves can be empowered to be more active agents (Escobar, 2018; Savickas, 2005) in shaping their careers specifically to increase their life and career satisfaction and their field more generally to contribute to a more egalitarian world (Sloane, 2019). The current authors support Walker's (2017) optimistic stance that designers can engage in holistic *Design for Life* in meaningful ways that diverge from capitalism and are more meaningful and sustainable and less destructive to society. Designers can use their ample creative skills to transform the system and their roles within that system to be more conducive to a society that allows them to contribute meaningful work to causes that advance humankind and help fulfill their own psychological needs while still being able to make a living wage.

REFERENCES

- Acemoglu, D. & Restrepo, P. (2019). Automation and new tasks: How technology displaces and reinstates labor. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 33(2), 3–30. <https://doi.org/10.1257/jep.33.2.3>
- Ahn, J., Dik, B. J. & Hornback, R. (2017). The experience of career change driven by a sense of calling: An interpretative phenomenological analysis approach. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 102, 48–62. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvb.2017.07.003>
- Bargdill, R. (2000). The study of life boredom. *Journal of Phenomenological Psychology*, 31(2), 188–219. <https://doi.org/10.1163/15691620051090979>
- Barnbrook, J. (n.d.) Q&A. Barnbrook. Retrieved from <https://barnbrook.net/education/qa/>
- Berg, J. M., Grant, A. M., & Johnson, V. (2010). When callings are calling: Crafting work and leisure in pursuit of unanswered occupational callings. *Organization Science*, 21(5), 973–994.
- Bunderson, J. S., & Thompson, J. A. (2009). The call of the wild: Zookeepers, callings and the double-edged sword of deeply meaningful work. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 54(1), 32–57. <https://doi.org/10.2189/asqu.2009.54.1.32>
- Chunharungroj, S. (October 22, 2020). In person interview by Ramon Sampatasatien.
- Danciu, V. (2014). Manipulative marketing: Persuasion and manipulation of the consumer through advertising. *Theoretical and Applied Economics*, XXI(2), 19–34.
- Deloitte (2017). The economic contribution of advertising in Europe: A report for the world federation of advertisers. Retrieved from https://www.owm.de/fileadmin/Archiv/public/downloads/publikationen/Value_of_Advertising_Executive_Summary_EUD.pdf
- Dik, B. J., & Duffy, R. D. (2009). Calling and vocation at work. *The Counseling Psychologist*, 37(3), 424–450. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0011000008316430>
- Duffy, R. D., & Autin, K. L. (2013). Disentangling the link between perceiving a calling and living a calling. *PsycheEXTRA Dataset*. <https://doi.org/10.1037/e619782013-001>
- Duffy, R. D., & Dik, B. J. (2013). Research on calling: What have we learned and where are we going? *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 83(3), 428–436. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvb.2013.06.006>

- Duffy, R. D., Allan, B. A., Autin, K. L., & Bott, E. M. (2013). Calling and life satisfaction: It's not about having it, it's about living it. *Journal of Counseling Psychology, 60*(1), 42–52.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/a0030635>
- Escobar, A. (2018). *Designs for the pluriverse: Radical interdependence, autonomy, and the making of worlds*. Duke University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1215/9780822371816>
- Garland, K. (1964). *First things first: A manifesto*. Goodwin Press. Retrieved from
<http://www.designishistory.com/1960/first-things-first/>
- Graeber, D. (2018). *Bullshit jobs: A theory*. Simon & Schuster.
<https://doi.org/10.37074/jalt.2018.1.2.17>
- Holland, J. L. (1997). *Making vocational choices: A theory of vocational personalities and work environments* (3rd ed.). Psychological Assessment Resources.
- Lau, P. L., Wilkins-Yel, K. G., & Wong, Y. J. (2020). Examining the indirect effects of self-concept on work readiness through resilience and career calling. *Journal of Career Development, 47*(5), 551–564.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0894845319847288>
- Liu, Z., Jiang, Y., Yao, Z., Liu, X., Zhao, L. & Zhang, X. (2021). Congruence in career calling and employees' innovation performance: Work passion as a mediator. *Chinese Management Studies*.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/CMS-12-2019-0427>
- Marx, K. (1847). *Wage labour and capital*. Retrieved from
<https://www.marxists.org/archive/marx/works/1847/wage-labour/ch02.htm>
- Relajo-Howell, D. (2018, April 12). How consumerism affects our well-being. *Psychreg*. Retrieved from
<https://www.psychreg.org/consumerism-well-being>
- Savickas, M.L. (2005). The theory and practice of career construction. In R. W. Lent & S. D. Brown (Eds.), *Career development and counseling: Putting theory and research to work*, 42–70. John Wiley.
- Seligman, M.E.P. (2011). Flourish: A visionary new understanding of happiness and well-being. *Choice Reviews Online, 48*(12), 48–7217. <https://doi.org/10.5860/choice.48-7217>
- Seligman, M.E.P. (1972). Learned helplessness. *Annual Review of Medicine, 23*(1), 407–412.
<https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.me.23.020172.002203>
- Sloane, M. (2019). On the need for mapping design inequalities. *Design Issues, 35*(4), 3–11.
https://doi.org/10.1162/desi_a_00559
- Van Tongeren, D.R., Green, J.D., Davis, D. E. Hook, J. N., & Hulsey, T. L. (2015). Prosociality enhances meaning in life. *The Journal of Positive Psychology, 11*(3), 225–236.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/17439760.2015.1048814>
- Walker, S. (2017). *Design for life: Creating meaning in a distracted world*. London: Routledge.
- Whiteley, N. (1985). Pop, consumerism, and the design shift. *Design Issues, 2*(2), 31.
<https://doi.org/10.2307/1511416>